

Survey Questions

General Questions:

What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Prefer not to say -----

What is the level of your academic study?

- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- PhD degree
- Other -----

What is your role in your organization?

- Data Scientist
- System/Business Analyst
- Requirements Engineer
- Software Engineer
- ML Specialists
- Quality Assurance Engineer
- Research and Development
- Other -----

How many years of experience do you have working with Artificial intelligence (AI)?

- Less than 3 years
- Between 3 to 5 years
- Between 6 to 10 years
- More than 10 years

How long have you been working in the industry?

- Less than 3 years
- Between 3 to 5 years
- Between 6 to 10 years
- Between 10 to 20 years
- More than 20 years

What type of organizations you build these solutions for?

- Government
- Defence
- Automotive
- Medicine / Health / Assistive Aid
- Agriculture / Food
- Manufacturing
- Entertainment
- Education
- Other -----

Which of the following Artificial Intelligence capabilities have you worked with? (You can select more than one)?

- Voice recognition
- Computer vision
- Image recognition
- Natural language processing
- Timeseries forecasting
- Anomaly detection
- Automated machinery
- Automated vehicles
- Clustering
- Classification
- Optimisation
- Other -----

Requirements / Modelling tools used

What type of requirements do you work with?

- Traditional (non-AI) functional requirements
- Traditional non – functional requirements
- AI system functional requirements
- AI system non – functional requirements
- AI system data requirements
- AI system user experience and user interface requirements
- Ethical requirements
- None – we do not have requirement’s when building AI systems
- Other -----

Which of the following methods have you used to elicit, analyse, specify, document, validate or manage requirements specifications when building AI systems? (You can select more than one)

- Goal-Oriented Requirements Engineering (e.g. i* and GORE)
- Use cases
- User stories
- Unified Modeling language (UML)
- Informal requirements (e.g. videos, audio)
- Documents (e.g. Word, Powerpoint)
- Our projects usually don’t include writing requirements
- Other -----

What tools do you use when writing or modelling requirements/specifications for Artificial Intelligence systems (e.g. Door, Word, Powerpoint, email, jUCMNav, MetaEdit+)?

What are the challenges or limitations you face when specifying requirements for Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems? (You can select more than one)

- Overestimating / overtrusting the capabilities of AI solutions
- Lack of clear feasibility of what AI models can and cannot do
- Defining requirements that are vague or hard to specify (e.g. defining a pedestrian to a self-driving car)

- AI requirements tend to be high-level, and no detailed specifications
- Limitations of existing Requirements Engineering techniques to manage AI requirements
- Capturing and specifying the trade-offs when building AI systems (e.g. precision vs recall or privacy vs explainability)
- The emergence of new types of requirements (such as data and ethic)
- Issues with data requirements such as lack of structure, availability or quality
- Do not know how to specify (or deal with) non-functional requirements in AI systems
- Providing inclusive design
- Dealing with biases in data
- Other -----

Human-centric Needs:

Area#1 - User Needs: Which of the following aspects of user needs do you capture during early stages of building Artificial Intelligence systems? (You can select more than one option)

- Identify the users of the system
- Identify why the system is needed
- Understand what the user expects from the system
- Decide on the feasibility of AI as a solution to some of these needs (use a non-AI solution instead)
- Specify whether the AI will be used for augmenting (assisting the user) or automation (automating the task for the user)
- Determine if the end-user needs to be aware of the AI feature used in the system or not
- Determine if the AI features interact with the user without requesting (proactive), vs reacts to the users request or interaction (reactive)
- Specify the trade-offs between the 'right' and 'wrong' predictions? i.e., precision vs recall
- Specify how to monitor the reward function values over time - i.e. when the Machine Learning model might need to be re-trained
- Our projects do not specify any user needs in the Requirements Engineering stage
- Other user needs that you identify in the Requirements Engineering stage?

Area#2 - Model requirements: Which of the following model needs do you specify when building Artificial intelligence systems? (You can select more than one option)

- Specify what the algorithm should optimize for? (e.g. explainability, accuracy, robust)
- If using Machine Learning, specify what task should be used (e.g. regression, classification, clustering)
- Specify which training method to use? Dynamic (improves and learns form user feed-back/behaviour) or static (trained offline, and only improves with updates)
- Specify how to balance between overfitting and underfitting
- Specify how to evaluate the model and which tools to use
- Specify the execution time or scalability issues
- Specify how user feedback is used in model tuning
- Specify how training data is used in model tuning
- Our projects do not specify any model requirements in the Requirements Engineering stage
- Other model requirements you would specify in the Requirements Engineering stage?

Area#3 - Data requirements: What data requirements do you consider when building Artificial intelligence systems? (You can select more than one option)

- Specify what data sources and datasets to use in model training and testing
- Specify how to split the dataset into training and testing sets
- Specify the minimum number of samples required

- Sampling rate (Number of samples collected over a specified timeframe)
- Specify how to label the data
- Specify the features to be present in the dataset
- Ensure the accuracy, coverage and correctness of data
- Ensure compliance with privacy and safety laws when collecting data
- Avoid and mitigate biases in the data
- Design for incoming data from user feedback
- Our projects do not specify any data requirements in the Requirements Engineering stage
- Other data requirements that you identify in the Requirements Engineering stage?

Area#4 - Feedback and User control: Which of the following do you consider during the requirements engineering phase of Artificial Intelligence systems? (You can select more than one option)

- Account for implicit feedback by monitoring users behaviours (e.g. the number of times they logged in, accepted/rejected recommendations)
- Account for explicit feedback by asking the users to provide feedback (e.g rankings, thumbs up, ask user to input textual feedback)
- Plan for explicit feedback by using surveys
- Specify and insure data privacy of personal information when collecting feedback
- Specify how user feedback is used to improve model performance
- Specify how user feedback is used in model tuning
- Specify when the user should take control over the system or when action is required – e.g. in a self-driving car
- Specify when and how users can adjust their preferences
- Our projects do not specify any feedback and user control needs in the Requirements Engineering stage
- Other requirements related to user feedback and control you would specify during the Requirements Engineering stage

Area#5 - Explainability & Trust: Which of the following explainability requirements do you consider when building Artificial Intelligence systems? (You can select more than one option)

- Explain the limitations of the AI system to the end user
- Explain the systems functionalities to the end user
- Explain the data sources to the end user and that predictions are based on data
- Provide an explanation to the output and why these prediction values were given
- Inform the user with any updates and changes done to the model or system
- Determine the level of detail needed to provide to the user – i.e. provide just enough explanation based on which task the user is doing at the moment
- Explain consequences to users' actions
- Accounting for explainability to conflict with other requirements such as performance, cost, development and security
- Avoid using predictions when confidence levels are low as it might create mistrust
- Do not provide an explanation, as it might be distracting or irrelevant
- Explain to the user how their information is used and shared (if any) with other vendors to avoid mistrust
- Our projects do not specify any explainability requirements in the Requirements Engineering stage
- Other explainability requirements you would specify during the Requirements Engineering stage

Q17 Area#6 - Errors and graceful failures: Which of the following would you specify during the requirements phase when building Artificial Intelligence? (You can select more than one option)

- Specify errors that might appear such as contexts, system and background errors

- Specify error sources that might occur such as models, data and user input
- Gather feedback to why users continue to reject predictions
- Avoid errors and incorrect assumptions that are made based on sensitive or private data
- Allow users to fix mistakes
- Lookout for abusive users
- Our projects do not specify how errors might occur or provide details of how to deal with failure in the RE stage
- Other requirements for errors and graceful failures you might specify in the Requirements Engineering stage

Do you have any other feedback for us on Requirements Engineering for AI/ML systems?

